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FROM SCHOOL TO HOME: UNDERSTANDING THE EXPERIENCES OF PARENTS AND LEARNERS IN MODULAR LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic brought a major shift in the delivery of instruction. Parents and learners were caught unprepared for this situation. As such, this study aimed to describe the experiences of parents and learners in modular learning. Following a phenomenological approach, 10 parents and 30 learners from the Schools Division of the City of Batac underwent unstructured interviews via home visits, phone calls, and messenger calls. It adopted the Hycner transcription analysis methodology for the data analysis. Findings revealed that parents' experiences could be described along four themes: multiple roles, learning management challenges, home learning strategies, and support systems. Meanwhile, learners' experiences were revealed by these four themes: learning preferences, learning struggles, learning strategies, and learning support. Interestingly, these experiences magnify the need for attention to shared responsibility, understanding, cooperation, commitment, and compassion for modular learning to succeed in the context of a pandemic. Furthermore, the findings could serve as a basis for providing comprehensive and inclusive educational policies that facilitate the adjustments of learners and parents in a new learning setup. Schools, therefore, can create and implement more adaptive, relevant, and inclusive institutional plans, projects, activities, and programs for the attainment of optimum learning experiences.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused unprecedented devastation across all domains, resulting in the closure of face-to-face educational operations in 190 countries and leaving over 1.2 billion children out of school worldwide

(Li & Lalani, 2020). This has forced a paradigm shift in the way teachers approach their jobs, as in-person lecture models do not work in a remote learning context, and they must juggle teaching, communication, and administrative tasks (Barron et al., 2021). To address these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented the Basic Education–Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) to safeguard the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and workers during COVID-19 while continuing education.

The Schools Division of the City of Batac (SDCB) has adopted modular learning as the preferred mode of delivery, allowing learners to accomplish modules at their own pace while improving their competencies (Lopez, 2020). However, self-paced learning can pose challenges for parents who may not be able to guide their children effectively (Acoba, 2020). To address these challenges, SDCB has actively monitored schools through field visits, 911 Klasrum, and other communication channels, while also acknowledging concerns about learning materials, assessment, and curriculum via social media and personal messaging.

Given the lack of research on the experiences of elementary learners and parents with modular distance learning, the SDCB has conducted a phenomenological study to explore these experiences further. This study generated useful data and identified trends that could inform the development of programs, activities, and projects to address concerns and create a more engaging modular learning environment. The study is divided into five parts, including an introduction, literature review, research methodology, data presentation and analysis, and result and discussion.

Overall, this study effectively highlights the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic to the educational landscape and how SDCB has adapted to these challenges. However, this could be improved by providing more specific examples of how SDCB has addressed challenges related to modular learning, as well as discussing potential limitations or challenges of the phenomenological study approach.

The study comprises five distinct parts. The first part is the introduction which sets the context for the study. The second part is the literature review which deepens the understanding of the topic and establishes its theoretical framework. Thirdly, the research methodology provides a detailed description of the methods used to collect and analyze data, ensuring that the study's results are valid and reliable. The fourth part presents the data that are analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques to identify patterns, trends, and relationships and analysis which presents the data which are gathered through interviews. The final part is the results and discussion. This explains the implications of the study's findings and their significance in the context of the research objectives. It also highlights the limitations of the study and offers recommendations for future research.

Literature Review

The purpose of the literature review is to deepen the understanding of the topic and establish its theoretical framework. The presentation of the literature review is arranged thematically.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Education

Due to lockdown and social distancing measures, schools and higher education facilities in most countries were closed (Sintema, 2020), leading to a shift towards distance learning programs such as online and modular learning (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). This transition was challenging for both learners and educators, who were not prepared for it (Donnelly et al., 2021; Petrie, 2020). As a result, many students experienced psychological and

emotional distress, and evidence suggests that school closures resulted in actual learning losses, particularly among students whose parents had less education.

Consequently, The Department of Education (DepEd) canceled classes and activities for the remaining weeks of SY 2019-2020 due to the pandemic. In SY 2020-2021, DepEd introduced the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP), which included streamlining the curriculum into essential competencies, using multiple learning delivery modalities, and providing self-learning modules. DepEd adopted materials from various partners, and learning outcomes were assessed through portfolios and summative tests.

Teachers and school leaders were prepared for multiple learning delivery modalities through capacity building consistent with DepEd's professional development framework and standards. They were introduced to various learning modalities and provided with tools to inform their decision-making. Capacity building took place from June to July 2020, and support mechanisms were established to provide technical and administrative guidance.

Local public health conditions were considered in adjusting the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) at the division level, with curriculum innovations encouraged to ensure safe and continuous learning at home. The Schools Division of the City of Batac responded contextually with the implementation of the localized BE-LCP based on research conducted by SDO personnel (Lopez, 2020). The plan included no face-to-face classes, coordination meetings with stakeholders, an MOU, and the adoption of printed modular learning. Teachers were assigned as subject and community teachers to assist learners with module completion and provide feedback.

Parents have played a crucial role in supporting their children's learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. While teachers have provided instruction, parents have acted as the "tagapagdaloy" or channel for their children's education. However, the pandemic has put significant pressure on parents, who face additional responsibilities beyond their role as a teacher at home. Studies by Alicamen and Abadiano (2020) and Bhamani et al. (2020) identified several themes related to parents' experiences with distance learning, including their acceptance of the educational challenge, actions taken to address the challenges, and strategies used to support learning at home. Additionally, parents have expressed concerns about maintaining a strict schedule, engaging in creative activities, and keeping children motivated and occupied. Despite these challenges, parents generally agreed with the school closure policy and appreciated the support provided by school districts while also identifying areas of struggle (Garbe, et al., 2020). Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the roles of parents as they have become learning facilitators at home to ensure their children's mastery of prescribed learning competencies.

Learners' Experiences in Distance Learning

The learners should always be at the forefront of the educative process. However, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has drastically impacted the educational landscape, particularly for students in underdeveloped nations. As noted by Alvarez (2020), the sudden outbreak has forced educational institutions to rapidly shift to a more challenging learning environment. Unfortunately, this has caused significant disruption and difficulties for many students who are struggling to adapt to the new educational norms.

Alvarez's (2020) phenomenological research revealed that learners thrust into remote learning during COVID-19 faced internet and financial constraints, lacked technology and emotional support, all of which impeded learning

engagement. Samortin et al. (2022) found deficient digital tools hampered active engagement and understanding, despite self-learning modules. Giray et al. (2022) noted respondents faced difficulties adjusting to online learning due to technology, mental health, finances, and time management.

Pokhrel and Chhetri (2021) noted students faced difficulties with online learning, such as caring for family members, tending to farm activities, and household chores. Symeonides and Childs (2015) added that written communication and lack of human interaction made it hard for learners to adapt to online learning. Better collaboration between students and tutors, academic and social support can increase student satisfaction and motivation in the online environment.

Despite the abrupt transition to distance learning, Yankey (2020) highlighted positive outcomes such as cost savings, flexible schedules, and improved time management. Distance learning also enhanced students' professional skills including self-study, problem-solving, responsibility, creativity, and initiative (Mahlangu, 2018). Literature suggests that adaptability, personal responsibility, peer connection, and time management are crucial for successful distance learning.

Statement of the Problems

This study aimed to explore how modular learning takes place during the pandemic through the experiences of parents and learners. For this purpose, answers were obtained from the following questions:

1. ***What are the experiences of the parents in modular learning?***
2. ***What are the experiences of the learners in modular learning?***

Assumption

The study assumes that modular learning at home can be determined by the experiences of parents and learners.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The learner group comprised 30 learners spread almost evenly along grade levels from kindergarten to Grade 5. They were purposively selected because they were enrolled in any public elementary school in the division during SY 2020–2021. Considering the level of maturity of these learners to be involved in a study such as this, the learning facilitators, such as grandparents, parents, and relatives, were tapped to substantiate the experiences described by the learner participants. The study limits its discussion to the experiences of learners and parents in modular learning.

Research Methodology

This study used semi-structured interviews with the participants to gather essential information. Initial questions about how the participants accepted the new learning set-up, how they adapted to it, and how they became persistent in their role were asked. Then, the researchers raised follow-up questions to dig deeper into their experiences. They were given the opportunity to provide illustrations, examples, and situations to elaborate on their significant experiences.

To ensure descriptive validity, an audio recorder on a cellphone was used with the interviewees' consent. It allowed the researchers to refer to the qualitative data that had been recorded in case some details were missed. They conducted a total of four home visits per participant, as well as several phone calls and messenger calls to further elucidate their responses as they moved forward with the initial data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed a phenomenological research design. Specifically, this study utilized descriptive phenomenology since (1) it is one of the most used methodologies in qualitative research within social sciences; (2) the phenomenon, which is modular learning in this pandemic explored in this study, relates to the field of education; and (3) this study asked the “experiences” of parents and learners, which is the central theme of this design.

The Locale of the Study

This study involved two groups of participants: the parent group and the learner group. There were 10 parents, 7 of them were working, and 3 were single parents. They were purposively selected based on these inclusion criteria: (1) have children enrolled in the public elementary schools of SDCB and (2) serve as the learning facilitator at home.

Data Gathering Instruments

The data were subjected to thematic analysis in accordance with Hycner's (1985) transcription analysis methodology. The researchers manually transcribed the recordings, extracted codes from the responses, clustered codes to generate categories, and determined themes from this cluster of meanings. The researchers repeatedly checked the codes, categories, and themes they had created to make sure their interpretations made sense.

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Ethical Consideration

The study ensured ethical considerations by implementing various measures. The participants were provided with informed consent forms, which outlined the nature and purpose of the study, as well as their right to voluntary participation and withdrawal at any time. In addition, the participants were given a thorough briefing before the study commenced. To ensure the involvement of the learners, their learning facilitators were also briefed about the study. These measures were taken to ensure that the study was conducted in an ethical and responsible manner.

Data Presentation and Analysis

1. What are the experiences of the parents in modular learning?

The parents shared their experiences with modular distance learning. Their responses led to the emergence of four major themes: multiple roles, learning management challenges, active learning preparations, and a strong support system.

Theme 1: Parents experienced multiple roles.

These refer to the experiences of working parents that revolve around their parental functions to ensure continuity of learning at home during the pandemic. Parents perform multiple roles such as monitor, collaborator, and learning resource provider to make modular distance learning successful for their children. As a learning monitor, parents set a goal with their children, identify what needs to be answered first, implement a homemade schedule, bring the child to work for close monitoring in answering the modules, and attend to the learning needs of the child by taking turns. The following statements by the participants could illustrate this role:

“We have a goal, ma’am. He must finish a module, so I can work also.” (P8)

“We agree on what subject to be answered first, especially that some subjects are difficult for them.” (P2)

“I can accommodate them, ma’am. I budget my time when I have my work from home. (P3)

“I bring my child to school to teach her. But, not on a Friday since it’s the module distribution of the school.” (P4)

“Sometimes, my husband would get the modules, especially if I was preoccupied with schoolwork. He would then get feedback from the teacher.” (P5)

Meanwhile, as learning collaborators, they plan out specific parental roles to perform considering the subjects to be assisted, establish constant communication with the subject teacher and community teacher, and seek assistance from their older children in monitoring the learning activities of their younger siblings while they are at work. As explicated by the participants:

“Because of our work, I and my husband divide the lessons to teach. My husband will teach Math and Science, while I take charge of Filipino and English.” (P1)

“If there are things we cannot understand, I would call his teacher.” (P8)

“The older sister will assist her, ma’am. When the modules arrive, I ask her sister to monitor her. She teaches the other lessons.” (P7)

Finally, in performing their role as a learning resource provider, they download videos and other learning resources for their children to watch and read; provide additional reading materials, like books, magazines, and newspapers; buy school materials like notebooks, and papers; set up a learning space, and prepare snacks during module time. This could be detailed in the following statements of the participants:

“During the lockdown, DepEd Commons was used to practice.” (P6)

“Before the opening, I bought notebooks already, ma’am.” (P9)

“We stay in the kitchen when doing the module ma’am because it is spacious and quiet. (P10)

“I prepare snacks ma’am because that’s what he asks for during module time. (P3)

Theme 2: Parents experienced various challenges in learning management.

This major theme pertains to various challenges parents encounter in managing their children's learning at home through modular distance learning. Such challenges immensely affect the way learning is delivered outside the

classroom setup. These could be learner-related, environment-related, parent-related, or learning resource-related. Parents were challenged with their children's behavior during module time. They noticed that their children immediately lose concentration, have short attention spans, are easily distracted, complain about tiredness in writing, are lazy at work, and are playful. These could be detailed from the responses of parents below:

"She has difficulty working when she is not in the mood. That is why I get mad at her sometimes." (P2)

"He would start working, then would stop until he does not complete his work." (P4)

"She is disturbed by her cousins because they do chitchats, or they teach each other." (P8)

"His gadget and cellphone disturb him, ma'am." (P9)

"Sometimes, she gets lazy in writing, ma'am. They (with her cousins) would ask for rest time. They often say that they are tired." (P6)

"Playful. While writing, he would say, Ma, I feel thirsty; I feel urinating." (P10)

Also, they experienced environment-related challenges, including distraction from co-learners, family members, and classmates, slow internet connection, COVID restrictions, lack of teacher's personal assistance/interface with learners, and financial constraints to provide loads for internet use. The following responses could point these out:

"We go to grandmother's house because she has younger siblings to disturb her. Sometimes, her sibling would also talk as she read. And she is disturbed." (P7)

"My problem, ma'am, is the internet connection. It's not always stable, ma'am." (P5)

"Because of COVID restrictions, he could not talk to his classmates or ask how to answer the modules." (P3)

"It is so difficult without the teacher to teach the learners. Learning is different without the teachers." (P4)

"I spent load for cellphone use since the Wifi connection is weak. So, I pay 100 pesos every week." (P1)

Parents also had challenges performing their roles because of conflict between work schedules and modular facilitation, difficulty in understanding modular contents, lack of confidence in teaching, insufficient time for modular teaching, the struggle in handling multiple learners at home, and lack of knowledge to use gadgets. The participants shared that:

"Modular learning is a challenge for working parents. In addition, there is limited time to monitor our children."

"For instance, I already forgot some of the lessons in Math, ma'am." (P4)

"Time would not be sufficient for me to teach all the lessons since I have work every weekday." (P8)

"I find it challenging to teach by myself, ma'am; I have my eldest, then her siblings. I find it challenging to teach the contents of the modules." (P10)

"I have limited knowledge of the use of gadgets. There are platforms that they use, which I do not know how." (P9)

Worries about learning resources compound parents' difficulties with modular education as they do not have available/sufficient learning support materials and too many modules and writing exercises to follow up.

"There are too many modules, especially in Mathematics, ma'am There are too many modules to accomplish and too difficult for his age." (P1)

"When writing long sentences, she would say, Ma, please do this part." (P5)

"We have no radio, ma'am. We have a television which can only access one channel. We have limited books where I can search for answers." (P6)

Theme 3: Parents employed home learning strategies to improve learning.

This major theme relates to the different activities done by parents to set and direct the mood of their children's learning process for modular learning. The employment of home learning strategies could be like what the teachers usually do in their classroom to encourage participation in accomplishing written, oral, and performance tasks.

Parents gave their children sufficient extrinsic motivation by promising gadgets and a nice staycation after the pandemic, buying their children's favorites, and permitting them to watch their favorite television or online shows after module time. As clearly stated by the participants:

"I told him to make good in his studies, I will buy him a cellphone." (P1)

"For me, I encouraged my children to continue their activities by promising them a vacation in Manila once the restrictions are lifted. They want to see their cousins." (P3)

"My child will tell me to finish his module if I allow him to watch his favorite cartoon. To encourage him, I would say, yes, sir." (P5)

"Because of the difficulties in managing learning, parents adjusted their schedules at the most convenient time for both and their children. These could be reflected by setting mornings and avoiding nighttime for module time, implementing a self-made WHLP, using weekends for the accomplishment of modules, and maximizing free time to let the child accomplish the modules." (P6)

"She only accomplishes the modules in the morning (9-12). She plays in the afternoon. In the evening, her sister (learning facilitator) also finishes her work, so she won't be disturbed. She does not work on modules in the evening because she sleeps early." (P8)

"We do not follow the schedule, (Weekly Home Learning Plan) ma'am because there are many things to be done." (P9)

"If I got the modules on Friday, we work on them on Saturday and Sunday since I am free." (P10)

Theme 4: Parents experienced a strong support system.

This major theme refers to the network of facilities and people helping the parents mitigate the challenges brought about by the pandemic in their demanding role as learning facilitators. The participants experienced a variety of forms of support, including the availability of a learning aid, additional learning resources, and a learning channel.

Parents are thankful to have been assisted by their relatives, older children, community teachers, and tutors. To further their children's understanding of the learning competencies, they relied on YouTube, DepEd Commons, and Google. These applications gave them more information so they could help their kids finish their modules. Also, parents utilized learning channels such as the 911 Klasrum, group messenger, phone calls, and short messaging systems to communicate with the subject teachers and the community teachers should there be issues or concerns.

The following statements could provide support for these findings:

"Sometimes, her ant would oversee her, ma'am, especially when we have many things to do." (P4)

"We request the community teacher to come, ma'am." (P5)

"If she comes with me in school, I am the one to teach her. However, if she stays at home, her older brother or daddy would help her." (P3)

"DepEd Commons could also be a source of reference materials ma'am." (P2)

“Should there be something he could not understand, we use Google.” (P6)

“I am grateful that there is 911 Klasrum which is a big help to raise our problems about the lessons.” (P1)

2. What are the experiences of the learners in modular learning?

The experiences of the learners during the pandemic could be described along these four major themes: learning preferences, learning struggles, learning strategies, and learning support system.

Theme 1: Learners had learning preferences in their modules.

Learners expressed that they liked and disliked some activities in the modules. To them, they love reading very short stories, drawing, coloring, making collages, and solving puzzles and number operations. This could be evident from these statements:

“I love reading stories, particularly in Filipino (children's stories). I learn many things, like do not steal.” (L1)

“I love accomplishing my modules especially when we have to draw a lot, ma'am. Drawing is my favorite activity.” (L3)

“I like doing collages. I use small pieces of paper or colored magazines.” (L4)

“I like activities with puzzles. It is easier to do.” (L17)

“I like solving, ma'am. I love addition and subtraction.” (L18)

On the contrary, they avoid doing activities related to note-reading, problem-solving, and writing long sentences.

“I don't like music so much, ma'am. I could hardly read notes.” (L20)

“I don't like Mathematics so much. Problem-solving is difficult.” (L15)

“I am not so interested in writing and copying long sentences.” (L5)

Theme 2: Learners experienced various struggles in learning.

These are associated with the obstacles that the students had to overcome to complete their assignments. They worked very hard to handle the module content, acclimate to their learning environment, and deal with the demands of their learning facilitators.

Learners explained that there were too many modules/activities in almost all learning areas; the activities in Mathematics, English, and MAPEH were so difficult; illustrative examples were insufficient; there were too many texts to read in science; directions were unclear; and English texts were difficult to understand. These could be reflected in these statements:

“The modules in Filipino are so bulky sometimes most especially when there are long stories, ma'am.” (L3)

“In Mathematics, I found out that most of the activities are difficult.” (L12)

“I cannot understand English if it is not translated in Ilokano like what ma'am _____ does in our school, ma'am.” (L19)

On the other hand, learners complained about home distractions, slow internet connection to access reference materials, non-existence of definite learning space, and unavailability of learning resources at home. As ascertained by them:

“The TV is open, so I don't want to have my module with my sister.” (L30)

“My internet connection fails, ma’am, so I could not find references for my modules. Sometimes, I could not send my outputs, ma’am.” (L28)

“I stay in different places, ma’am. Sometimes, I am in the kitchen, receiving area, outside the house, or in my room. I choose a quiet, ma’am.” (L14)

“I don’t have reference materials to use at home, sir.” (L17)

Furthermore, they gave up on some activities since their learning facilitators could not be of help because of their inadequate knowledge of the contents of the modules, insufficient time to attend to their learning needs, unfavorable health conditions due to old age, and inability to understand the language used in the module. The participants shared that:

“If sickness attacks my grandfather, ma’am, we don’t have any choice because my parents go home late at night.” (L20)

“My mother sometimes does not know the contents of our module, sir. As such, I just copy the answer to our module, sir.” (L24)

“My father had difficulty explaining the lesson ma’am because he could hardly understand English, ma’am.” (L23)

Theme 3. Learners adopted different strategies to lessen the burden of home-based learning.

Despite the challenges caused by the pandemic, learners were able to manage them by adopting different strategies. These strategies include selecting a motivating learning space at home and setting up a flexible schedule to answer modules.

In their desire to find a comfortable space at home to do their modules, learners stayed on the balcony, porch, kitchen/dining area, sala (receiving area), bedroom, and veranda. These are the excerpts from the participants:

“I stay on the porch ma’am because my older sister stays inside with the TV open and it’s far from my mom if I stay here in my grandmother’s front yard.” (L29)

“We stay in the living room for my module. But sometimes, my younger brother disturbs me so we transfer to the bedroom.” (L30)

“We stay in the kitchen when doing the module ma’am because it is spacious and quiet.” (L18)

Since their learning facilitators could only help them at their convenience, they adjusted and agreed to adopt a flexible schedule to answer modules. They explored one module per session (AM/PM), one module for two days, a cluster of modules in a day, modules until Thursday, and set Friday as a play day, and their favorite subject and easy activities first. As the participants subscribed:

“If my Lola brings home my modules, I do not answer them immediately. I will answer one module the next day and the other one will be on the following day.” (L8)

“If there are two or three lessons in the module, we answer it by lesson. I prefer my lesson so that she could master it. We answer the module until Thursday because if we are done, she will just play and play.” (L3)

“I do first easier ones like connecting and encircle followed by the harder activities.” (L2)

Theme 4: Learners had a strong learning support system.

Undeniably, learners survived the first school year under the pandemic with the presence of a strong learning support system. This support system includes the learning facilitators, learning resources, and the learning channel.

During the pandemic, their parents, relatives, tutors, older siblings, and community teachers have become their partners in learning. Their home learning facilitators have been regarded as MKOs or More Knowledgeable Others, rather than just being related by blood. They provided the learners with examples and explanations to understand the lessons learned from the modules. The participants clearly pointed out:

“My aunt is the one who teaches me because my mother works abroad.” (L12)

“My mother teaches me because she is always in the house. She does not go to work.” (L14)

“If mom is not present ma'am, my older sister and cousins (referring to older sister and cousins) will help me.” (L2)

“The tutor will read the text for me because I cannot read yet.” (L1)

With different learning resources such as Google, DepEd Commons, Youtube videos, Facebook learning pages, and blogs, learners were able to find additional information to expound the explanations in the modules and activity sheets. These are evident from the statements of the participants:

“We use Google, DepEd Commons, and Youtube videos to clearly understand our lesson. There is also an FB page created by our teacher where we could watch video lessons, sir.” (L22)

The learners relied also on the use of the 911 Klasrum, group messaging, and phone calls for communicating with their subject teachers about the difficult contents, which both and their learning facilitators could not comprehend.

As shared by the participants:

“We use the 91 Klasrum if the teacher informs us and if we ask something.” (L26)

“Our teacher will chat the parts of our lesson that we could not understand, sir.” (L28)

“My mother will call my teacher, ma'am.” (L16)

Results and Discussion

During the pandemic, parents have taken on multiple roles to ensure their children meet minimum learning competencies and experience comfort, safety, and ease of learning (Daniela, et al., 2021). However, they face learning management challenges (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017; Montera, 2013; McConville, 2019, and Wang, 2020), and the adoption of relevant and responsive means to resolve them is necessary. Parents' involvement in their children's education reflects a lasting resilience in education, and their support system is vital in keeping learning going despite the pandemic. Lardizabal-Dado (2020; Bhamani et al. (2020); Mahuro and Hungi (2016) Learners have various difficulties related to modular learning, including a lack of interest in certain subjects and maladaptation to the new learning setup as pointed out by Yan, et al. (2021). The support system established, as pointed out by Shafiei Sarvestani et al. (2019), has eased their negative experiences; and their preferences and experiences should be considered in making decisions for future educational programs. Moreover, understanding both parents' and learners' experiences can inform decision-making for projects, activities, and programs under these exceptional circumstances (Hernandez-Hernandez & Sancho-Gil, 2021).

Conclusion

Due to the pandemic and COVID-19 restrictions, education has shifted to home learning via distance, homeschooling, and remote learning. Parents have adapted to their new roles and become persistent with support. Modular learning has instigated experiences and challenges that activated single parents' readiness and commitment. Shared responsibility, understanding, cooperation, commitment, and compassion are necessary for success with the modular approach during the pandemic.

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